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NEW AGE PEOPLE'S LIBRARY: THE FUTURE OF PUBLIC LIBRARIES IN NORTH EAST INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The study explores the evolving landscape of public libraries in North East India, a culturally diverse region comprising eight states. It discusses transitioning from traditional to technology libraries that embrace digital resources, community engagement, and modernisation. It also highlights the challenges public libraries face, such as infrastructure limitations, linguistic diversity, and funding constraints. The data have been collected from various secondary documents and websites. Most public libraries in the Northeast Region have not been registered with the Raja Rammohun Roy Library Foundation (R.R.L.F.). The paper analyses the status of public libraries in North East Indian states concerning districts and the number of villages. It also addresses the necessity for enacting library legislation and establishing a Library Association of North East India. The study underscores the importance of library digitization in making knowledge more accessible. Furthermore, it emphasises the role of government support, community engagement, cultural preservation, and infrastructure development in shaping the future of the public.

Keywords: Public library, New age people's library, Digital library, Digital revolution, North East India.

Introduction

The Northeast region of India, comprising eight distinct states, is a cultural mosaic with a rich tapestry of languages, traditions, and histories. Public libraries promote education, preserve heritage, and foster community in this diverse and dynamic landscape.

A public library is established, supported, and funded by the community through local, regional, or national government or other community organisations. It provides access to knowledge, information, and works of the imagination through various resources and services. It is equally available to all community members, irrespective of race, nationality, age, gender, religion, language, disability, economic status, or educational background.

The public library system in Northeast India has evolved over the years, adapting to changing socio-cultural dynamics and technological advancements. Traditionally, these libraries have been sanctuaries of knowledge, offering the public books and other printed materials. However, the future of public libraries in the region will be shaped by a convergence of factors, including technology, changing user preferences, and the necessity to cater to a broader spectrum of community needs. This public library network encompasses urban and rural areas, and modernization must permeate every aspect of society. Public libraries should execute compelling programs to cater to this evolution.

In this era of digital information and instant connectivity, public libraries in North East India must undergo a metamorphosis to retain their relevance and vibrancy. The future of these libraries will likely see them transform

into multidimensional hubs for learning, innovation, and community engagement, going beyond their traditional role as repositories of books .

New Age People's Libraries

New age People's Libraries represent a modern and dynamic approach to the traditional concept of libraries. These libraries are designed to cater to today's society's diverse and evolving needs, reflecting the changing landscape of information and technology. Unlike traditional libraries, which primarily focus on physical books and printed materials, New Age People's Libraries embrace digital resources, interactive learning tools, and community engagement . These libraries embrace technology to provide digital resources, e-books, and online databases, ensuring that information is readily available to anyone with an internet connection. They also offer collaborative learning, creativity, and social interaction spaces, encouraging community engagement and fostering a sense of belonging. Moreover, these libraries often feature programs and workshops that address contemporary challenges and interests, such as coding classes, financial literacy seminars, wellness workshops, and discussions on current social issues. They aim to be inclusive, accessible, and welcoming to all demographics, recognizing that learning and information-seeking take various forms in today's fast-paced, digital world.

Role of Public Libraries

The traditional role of public libraries has been multifaceted, serving as vital community hubs and repositories of knowledge for generations. These institutions have historically provided free access to a wide range of printed materials, including books, magazines, newspapers, and reference materials, making them essential resources for individuals seeking information and self-improvement . Public libraries have also been instrumental in promoting literacy and lifelong learning, offering programs and services that cater to people of all ages and backgrounds. Moreover, they have played a crucial role in bridging the digital divide by providing computer and internet access, enabling people to participate in the digital age. Beyond the physical collections, libraries have also served as community gathering spaces, hosting events, lectures, workshops, and programs that promote cultural enrichment, lifelong learning, and social interaction. Public libraries have played a fundamental role in democratizing information, enriching lives, and empowering individuals to explore the world of knowledge, making them integral institutions within our societies' .

Public Libraries in North East India

The North Eastern Region comprises seven states, popularly known as the seven sisters. In 2001, the eighth state, 'Sikkim,' was included in the North Eastern Region . These states are Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, and Tripura.

Each state has its own branch of public libraries . The data used for this information have been gathered from various sources, including electronic journals, websites, and more.

Table 1: State-wise Number of Public Libraries in North East India

Table 1 displays the overall scenario of public libraries in the Northeastern states of India. These libraries are observed at various levels: state, district, town, divisional/sub-divisional, block, rural, aided/grant-in-aid, and NGO-operated libraries. The data reveals 2,487 public libraries in North East India, and Mizoram leads with the highest count of 991 public libraries.

Table 1: State-wise Number of Public Libraries in North East India

Name of the States	State Central Libraries	District Central Libraries	City Library/ Town Libraries	Divisional /Sub-Divisional Library	Branch/ Block Libraries	Rural libraries	Aided/G rant in Aid Libraries	NGO Libraries	Total
Arunachal Pradesh	1	21	2	22	34	72	-	-	152
Assam	1	26	-	15	33	199	-	-	274
Manipur	1	12	-	-	1	44	-	144	202
Meghalaya	1	7	-	-	--	-	-	86	94
Mizoram	1	5	-	-	-	485	-	500	991
Nagaland	1	11	-	-	-	610	-	-	622
Sikkim	1	3	-	6	-	-	4	3	17
Tripura	1	7	1	10	6	10	-	100	135
Total	8	92	3	53	74	1420	4	833	2487

Table 2: Average Number of Registered Libraries in RRRLF

Name of the States	Numbers of Public Library	Registered Library in RRRLF (%)
Arunachal Pradesh	152	92(60.53%)
Assam	274	108(39.42%)
Manipur	202	169(83.67%)
Meghalaya	94	5(5.32%)
Mizoram	991	266(26.85%)
Nagaland	622	31(4.99%)
Sikkim	17	4(23.53%)
Tripura	135	29(21.49%)
Total	2487	704(28.31%)

The total number of registered libraries in the North East States concerning the Raja Ram Mohan Roy Library Foundation is illustrated in Table 2. It is found that Manipur has the highest number of libraries (83.67%) registered with RRRLF. On the other hand, Nagaland has the lowest number of registered libraries, comprising only 4.99% of the total libraries.

Table 3: Library Act Passed and Library Association (North East State-Wise)

Sl No.	Name of the States	Library Act (Year)	Library Association (Year)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	2009	No Library Association
2	Assam	No Library Act	1938
3	Manipur	1988	1987
4	Meghalaya	No Library Act	1994
5	Mizoram	1993	1987
6	Nagaland	No Library Act	1996
7	Sikkim	No Library Act	No Library Association
8	Tripura	No Library Act	1967

Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, and Mizoram are the only states among the eight states of North East India mentioned in Table 3 that have enacted library legislation. Interestingly, neither Arunachal Pradesh nor Sikkim has a library association. The Assam Library Association, established in 1938, is the first library association in the northeastern region. In 1964, Dr. S. R. Ranganathan drafted a public library bill, which was subsequently handed over to the government of Assam for Library Legislation by the Assam Library Association.

Table 4: State-Wise Distribution of Public Library Under Ministry

Sl No.	Name of the States	Under Department	Ministry
1	Arunachal Pradesh	Directorate of Public Libraries	Libraries
2	Assam	Cultural Affairs Department, Assam	Cultural Affairs
3	Manipur	Department of Art and Culture, Manipur	Art & Culture
4	Meghalaya	Department of Art and Culture, Meghalaya	Art & Culture
5	Mizoram	Department of Art and Culture, Mizoram	Art & Culture
6	Nagaland	Directorate of Art and Culture	Art & Culture
7	Sikkim	Cultural Affairs & Heritage Department	Cultural Affairs and Heritage
8	Tripura	Higher Education Department	Higher Education

In most of Northeast India, public libraries are controlled by the Ministry of Art & Culture. However, in Tripura, public libraries fall under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Higher Education, while in Arunachal Pradesh, the Ministry in charge of Library Services manages library affairs. These administrative arrangements reflect the diverse governance structures in the region, with different ministries taking responsibility for managing and promoting public libraries in their respective states.

Table 5. Average of District libraries and Village Libraries on Total no. of Districts and Villages

Sl No.	Name of the States	No. of District	No. of District Libraries (%)	No. of Villages	No. of Village Libraries (%)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	26	21(80.77%)	5587	72(1.29%)
2	Assam	33	26(78.79%)	18,700	199(1.07%)
3	Manipur	16	12(75%)	2581	44(1.71%)
4	Meghalaya	11	7(63.64%)	6500	Not Found
5	Mizoram	11	5(45.46%)	719	485(67.46%)
6	Nagaland	11	11(100%)	1355	610(45.02%)
7	Sikkim	4	3(75%)	448	Not Found
8	Tripura	8	7(87.6%)	856	10(1.17%)
9	Total	119	92(77.32%)	36746	1420(3.87%)

Table 5 shows that Nagaland comprises 11 districts, each boasting 100% coverage of district libraries. In contrast, Mizoram has only 45.46% of the total district libraries within its 11 districts. Furthermore, in Mizoram, village libraries constitute 67.46% of the library's presence in rural areas, whereas Assam has the lowest percentage of village libraries, a mere 1.07%, in village areas. Regrettably, Meghalaya and Sikkim have not reported the existence of any village libraries.

Digital Revolution and Public Libraries of India

Today, we live in exciting times, and digital libraries are the most important development in the 21st century. The information revolution supplies the appropriate technology for creating digital libraries and provides the unprecedented demand for storing, organizing, and accessing information. Here are some key ways in which the digital revolution has influenced public libraries:

- **Access to Digital Resources:** Public libraries have adapted to the Digital Revolution by providing various digital resources, including e-books, audiobooks, digital magazines, and online databases. This allows patrons to access content anywhere, anytime, using their computers, eReaders, tablets, or smartphones.
- **Digital Literacy Programs:** Public libraries are crucial in promoting digital literacy. They offer classes and workshops on computer skills, online safety, and digital literacy, helping patrons navigate the digital world effectively.
- **Internet Access:** Public libraries have become crucial free internet access providers to those who may not have it at home. It helps bridge the digital divide and ensures that individuals have access to essential online resources, job searches, educational materials, and government services.
- **Digital Archives:** Public libraries often serve as repositories for digital archives and local history collections.

They preserve historical documents, photographs, and other materials in digital formats, making them accessible for future generations.

- **Collaboration with Schools and Educational Institutions:** Public libraries often collaborate with schools and educational institutions to provide digital resources and support for students and educators. This partnership enhances learning opportunities outside the classroom.
- **Remote Access:** Remotely accessing library resources has become increasingly important. Patrons can borrow e-books and audiobooks from home, access online research databases, and use library resources without physically visiting the library.
- **Library Catalogues and Online Services:** Libraries have transitioned their catalogue systems and services online. Patrons can search for books, place holds and renew materials through library websites and apps. Online library catalogue has become more user-friendly and efficient.

Challenges Faced by Public Libraries in North East India

Public libraries in Northeast India face unique challenges due to the region's geographical, cultural, and socioeconomic diversity (Lalnunpuia, 2019; . While these challenges may vary from state to state and even within different parts of the area, some common issues include:

- **Infrastructure and Connectivity:** In many parts of the Northeast region, inadequate infrastructure and poor connectivity hinder the establishment and functioning of libraries. Lack of electricity, maintenance, and internet access hampers the digitization of library resources and the implementation of modern library management systems. Additionally, many remote areas may not have easily accessible libraries, making it challenging for residents to use their services.
- **Geographical Isolation:** North East India is geographically isolated due to hilly terrain, dense forests, and the region's location between neighbouring countries like Bhutan, China, and Myanmar. This geographical isolation makes establishing and maintaining libraries challenging, as transportation and infrastructure development can be difficult and costly.
- **Linguistic and Cultural Diversity:** North East India is known for its rich linguistic and cultural diversity, with numerous indigenous languages and ethnic communities. This diversity poses challenges in cataloging, acquiring materials, and providing services in multiple languages.
- **Limited Funding:** Public libraries in the North East often struggle to secure sufficient funding for their operations and expansion. This limitation affects acquiring new books, technology upgrades, and hiring qualified staff, impacting the quality of library services.
- **Lack of Awareness:** Many people in the region may not be aware of the benefits of using public libraries or may not have easy access to information about library services. Promoting library services and conducting outreach programs to raise awareness is a significant challenge.
- **Maintenance and Preservation:** Libraries must invest in proper maintenance and preservation techniques to protect their collections from environmental damage due to the region's high humidity and heavy rainfall.
- **Environmental Challenges:** The region is prone to natural disasters such as floods, landslides, and earthquakes. Public libraries may need to invest in disaster preparedness and recovery plans to protect their collections and infrastructure.
- **Security Concerns:** In some areas of North East India, security concerns and conflicts may affect the operation of public libraries. These challenges can impact the safety of library staff and patrons and the accessibility of library

resources.

Library Digitization

Digitization converts analogue information into a digital format, making it accessible and manipulable through electronic devices and computer systems. This process encompasses converting various forms of media, including texts, images, audio, and video, into binary code, which computers can represent and process. This revolutionary advancement has profoundly impacted numerous sectors, including libraries, archives, museums, and businesses, ushering in new global information dissemination, research, and collaboration opportunities. Today, digitization is a central topic in librarianship, focusing on creating "digital libraries" by making collection content available electronically. The fustian of the information highway has provided the impetus to convert many existing paper-based (sound, video) collections into new digital media. The assumption is that digital collections will be more accessible to a broader range of users, presumably through networking techniques. New efficiencies will be gained in resource sharing and preservation.

Library digitization utilizes computers, databases, multimedia equipment, and web technologies to collect, classify, copy, compress, scan, and transform conventional library information resources electronically. Library digitization aims to preserve and make cultural and educational resources more widely available to the public by leveraging digital technologies. It allows for easier cataloguing, searchability, and remote access to valuable information, expanding the reach and impact of libraries in the digital age.

Library digitization differs from a digital library as it makes diverse library information resources available electronically. In contrast, a digital library is a platform for accessing, collecting, managing, searching, and storing distributed digitized information resources over the Internet and the World Wide Web.

Thus, network technology is crucial in providing access to these digitized library projects that offer digitized resources. The primary goal of library digitization is to make the content of libraries and archives more accessible to a broader audience by providing online or electronic versions that can be easily searched, accessed, and preserved. Digitization can also help protect fragile or deteriorating materials by reducing the need for physical handling.

Future for Public Libraries in North East India

The prospects for public libraries in North East India depend on various factors, including local initiatives, government support, community involvement, technological advancements, and changing educational and reading habits; . Here are some potential prospects for public libraries in North East India:

- **Government Support:** The future of public libraries in Northeast India will depend on government policies and funding. Advocacy for increased government support can ensure the sustainability and growth of these institutions.
- **Digital Transformation:** Like libraries worldwide, public libraries in North East India are likely to embrace digital transformation. Prospects include expanding their digital collections and providing e-books, online courses, and digital literacy programs. These initiatives can help reach a wider audience, especially in remote areas.
- **Community Engagement:** Public libraries need to engage with their communities to remain relevant actively. It can involve hosting events, workshops, and activities catering to the residents' needs and interests. These libraries can become community hubs for learning, culture, and social interaction.
- **Cultural Preservation:** With the rich cultural diversity of the Northeast, public libraries can take on a role in preserving and promoting local culture and heritage. They may collect and archive traditional knowledge, folklore, and indigenous literature, making them accessible to future generations.

- **Infrastructure Development:** The physical infrastructure of libraries should be maintained and upgraded to provide a comfortable and conducive environment for reading and learning. Accessible locations and well-designed buildings can attract more patrons.
- **Collaborations:** Public libraries can strengthen their roles by collaborating with local schools, universities, NGOs, and government agencies. These partnerships can help share resources and funds and develop specialized programs.
- **Sustainability Initiatives:** Public libraries may have implemented sustainability initiatives, such as green building practices, energy-efficient technologies, and eco-friendly programs that promote environmental awareness.
- **Mobile Libraries:** Given the geographical challenges of the North East, mobile libraries or bookmobiles can play a significant role in reaching remote areas. These portable units can bring books and educational resources to underserved communities.
- **Education and Lifelong Learning:** Public libraries will continue to play a crucial role in supporting teaching and lifelong learning. They may partner with local schools, colleges, and educational institutions to offer student resources and support.
- **Online Services:** Online catalogue access, reservations, and virtual programming can become more integral to library services, providing users convenience and flexibility.
- **Open Access Initiatives:** Public libraries could actively participate in open access initiatives, advocating for and providing access to available educational resources (OER) and open-access research publications.

Conclusion

The evolving landscape of libraries in the modern era reflects a dynamic shift toward meeting society's diverse and changing needs. New-age People's libraries embrace digital resources, technology, and community engagement to provide accessible and inclusive services. On the other hand, traditional public libraries play a vital role in our communities, offering access to printed materials, promoting literacy, and serving as cultural hubs.

However, public libraries in North East India face unique challenges, including infrastructure limitations, geographical isolation, linguistic diversity, and funding issues. Despite these challenges, there is a current effort to establish and maintain libraries in the region, with some states passing Public Libraries Acts and various library initiatives;

The digitization of libraries plays a crucial role in making information more accessible and preserving cultural heritage. It allows for easier cataloguing, searchability, and remote access to valuable information, extending the reach of libraries in the digital age. The digital revolution has significantly influenced public libraries globally by providing access to digital resources, promoting digital literacy, offering internet access, preserving digital archives, and facilitating collaboration with educational institutions. Public libraries in North East India can benefit from these trends by embracing digital transformation and engaging with their communities.

Looking ahead, the future of public libraries in North East India depends on factors like government support, digital transformation, community engagement, and collaborations. These libraries have the potential to not only serve as information hubs but also as centres for cultural preservation, education, and sustainability. Embracing online services, open-access initiatives, and mobile libraries can enhance regional reach and impact. Public libraries remain essential for knowledge and community building in the digital age.

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